

MEASUREMENT OF FIBER-MATRIX ADHESION AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO COMPOSITE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

by

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ABSTRACT

Results are reported on a well characterized experimental system consisting of an epoxy matrix and carbon fibers was selected wherein only the fiber surface chemistry was altered to produce three different degrees of adhesion. Embedded single fiber fragmentation tests were conducted to quantify the level of fiber matrix adhesion. Observation of the events occurring at the fiber breaks led to the documentation of three distinct failure modes coincident with the three levels of adhesion. The lowest level produced a frictional debonding, the intermediate level produced interfacial crack growth and the highest level produced radial matrix fracture.

High fiber volume fraction composites made from the same material were tested for on and off-axis as well as fracture properties. Results indicate that composite results can be explained if both differences in adhesion and failure mode are considered. It will be further demonstrated that fiber-matrix adhesion is an "optimum" condition that has to be selected for the stress state that the interface will experience. The embedded single fiber fragmentation test is both a valuable measurement tool for quantifying fiber-matrix adhesion as well as the one method which provides fundamental information about the failure mode necessary for understanding the role of adhesion on composite mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion, Composites, Fiber, Matrix, Bonding.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is very desirable to have a testing method to measure the adhesion between fiber and matrix which can provide a reproducible, reliable method for investigating and measuring fiber-matrix adhesion. Several testing methods were developed for measuring fiber-matrix adhesion using single fibers or groups of fibers. The goal was to measure fiber-matrix adhesion in a way that would be a predictor of composite fiber-matrix adhesion as well as to understand the fundamental physics and chemistry of adhesion itself. Although there have been a wide variety of methods proposed in recent years, most can be reduced to three basic measurement methods. They are: fiber pull-out methods; fiber fragmentation methods; and fiber micro-compression methods. The pull-out methods and the microindentation methods provide a measure of the strength of the fiber-matrix bond. The fragmentation test also provides a method to measure the fiber-matrix bond strength but at the same time gives information about the interfacial failure mode. A recent review contains a detailed literature survey of different single fiber methods and a comparison of the assumptions and limitations which are inherent in each one¹.

The ultimate purpose of this research is to deduce the mechanisms and principles responsible for fiber-matrix adhesion and the relationship between the interfacial properties measured by this method with actual composite properties.

2. BACKGROUND

In order to serve as the experimental system to explore the relationships between fiber-matrix adhesion, the embedded single fiber fragmentation test method and composite mechanical properties, a carbon fiber-epoxy system has been selected as a standard composite material system. One carbon fiber with three different surface treatments combined with a low temperature amine cured epoxy has been the object of a detailed interfacial and composite property research program.

2.1 Polymeric Matrix. An epoxy-amine matrix system was selected for this study. This chemistry is representative of the majority of composite applications². The reactants can be processed at low temperatures and the properties of the resultant matrix are typical for a high performance matrix. A di-functional epoxy, diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol-A (DGEBA) at stoichiometric conditions (14.5 phr meta-phenylene diamine) was mixed, debulked and processed for 2 hours at 75°C and 2 hours at 125°C for both single fiber and composite coupons.

2.2 Reinforcing Fibers. The polyacrylonitrile based carbon fibers chosen for this study are the A-4 fibers (Hercules, Inc.) having a fiber tensile modulus of about 238 GPa and tensile strength is 3.6 GPa when measured at a 25mm gage length. The fibers were provided with three different surface conditions. "AU4" fibers are "as-received" that is, removed from the heat treatment ovens without any further surface treatment. "AS4" fibers are surface treated with an electrochemical oxidation step which optimizes the adhesion to epoxy matrices and "AS4C" fibers are coated with a 100-200 nm layer of epoxy applied from an organic solvent directly onto the surface treated AS-4 fibers. These fibers are circular in cross-section.

2.3 Composite Specimens. Unidirectional composite prepregs were fabricated from the three batches of carbon fibers i.e. AU-4, AS-4, and AS-4C. The impregnation was done using a hot-melt prepregger with a slit die (Research Tool Corporation). The curing cycle was 0.69 Mpa (100 psi) for two hours at 75°C (167°C) followed by 2 hours at 125°C (257°C). Vacuum was vented for 15 minutes in the 75°C (167°C) soak. The laminate was cooled to ambient temperature before removal from the autoclave.

Fiber volume fraction and void content of unidirectional specimens were determined by optical numeric volume fraction analysis (ONVFA) which is described in detail³. The volume fraction of fibers was kept around 67% for all of the panels. The mechanical characterization tests that were conducted in this study were 0° and 90° tension (ASTM D-3039), 0° compression (ASTM D-3410), 0° and 90° three-point flexure (ASTM D-790), ±45° tension (ASTM D-3518) and Iosipescu shear tests for inplane shear characterization, short-beam shear test (ASTM D-2344) for interlaminar shear characterization, and double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notched flexure (ENF) tests for Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, respectively. The ASTM specifications (when available) were used for specimen dimensions and testing procedures. The Iosipescu shear tests were performed according to the procedure outlined elsewhere⁴. The DCB and ENF testings were performed according to the published procedures⁵. At least ten specimens were tested for each type of test. All the tests were performed on a closed-loop servohydraulic MTS testing machine. The fracture surfaces of failed specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the effect of fiber-matrix adhesion on the major failure modes were determined.

2.4 Previous Work. The surface chemical and topographical features of these reinforcing fibers have been characterized using a variety of techniques and the results reported in detail elsewhere^{6,7,8}. The fibers whether surface treated or untreated have the same surface area as measured by gas adsorption. They differ in their surface chemistry primarily in the amount of surface oxygen groups and nitrogen groups present. Wettability measurements on these fibers show that the surface free energy is greater than that of the matrix insuring thermodynamic compatibility. On an absolute basis less than 5% of the surface sites of the carbon fiber are involved in chemical bonding⁹.

The embedded single fiber fragmentation test has been used to provide a measure of the level of fiber-matrix adhesion for this fiber-matrix combination. Table I shows the value of the interfacial shear strength from this single fiber fragmentation test. There is a large increase in the interfacial shear strength with surface treatment (AS4) and a further increase with the application of the fiber finish (AS4C). The concurrent observation of the fiber photoelastic stress pattern and microtoming of the resultant interphase provide an explanation for the changes observed with surface treatment. There is a two-part process associated with the electrolytic surface anodization used with carbon fibers. Not only are surface oxygens and other species added in the surface treatment process, but the native fiber surface that has undergone the graphitization step during the conversion of the polyacrylonitrile to graphite is removed by the surface treatment. The etching away of the native fiber surface and the addition of surface oxygen groups increase the concentration to about twice the level initially present on the fiber surface before surface treatment. Ultramicrotome sectioning and TEM examination show that the failure of the "as-received" AU4 interface is through the outer layer of the carbon fiber while pure interfacial failure results after surface treatment. This result shows that after surface treatment, the initial defect

laden surface has been replaced by a surface which is capable of sustaining high mechanical loads without failure. This increase in structural integrity is responsible for the majority of the improvement in adhesion. The addition of the surface chemical oxygen groups is responsible for only 10% of the increase in adhesion.

In addition to the use of surface treatments which are primarily chemical in nature, surface finishes or coatings are also used to affect fiber-matrix adhesion. The surface treated carbon fibers coated with 100 nanometers of an epoxy resin without any curing agent (AS4C) were processed as usual and the level of adhesion was measured with the embedded single fiber critical length test⁸. The level of interfacial shear stress that the interface could withstand increased by about 25%. The mechanism by which this surface finish increases the level of fiber-matrix adhesion is through an interaction with the bulk matrix which causes a local change in properties in the fiber-matrix interphase. Model compounds prepared of epoxy stoichiometry known to be possible in the interphase were prepared and processed in a manner identical to the composite. Measurements of strength, stiffness and fracture toughness of variable epoxy/amine stoichiometries with the amine to epoxy ratio less than stoichiometric combined with optical micrographs of the fiber-matrix interface under stress show that the increase in the adhesion level is due to better stress transfer between fiber and matrix. The modulus of epoxy-rich stoichiometries increases but the material also becomes more brittle¹⁰. Because of the more brittle interface, matrix cracking is detected at fiber breaks instead of fiber-matrix interfacial failure as seen in other interfacial conditions.

RELATIONSHIP OF COMPOSITE PROPERTIES TO FIBER-MATRIX ADHESION AND THE INTERPHASE

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The set of three fibers, AU-4, AS-4 and AS-4C, combined with the amine cured epoxy matrix, provides the quantitative basis for developing structure-property relationships between fiber-matrix adhesion and composite mechanical properties. The data in Table 1 show that there are significant changes in adhesion as measured

**Table 1. Properties of the Fibers and Matrix,
Interfacial Shear Strengths and Failure Modes**

Material	Tensile Modulus(Gpa)	Tensile Strength(GPa)	Intf.Shear Strength(MPa)	Interfacial Failure Mechanism
AU4	234.4	3.58	37.2	Poor Interfacial
AS4	234.4	3.58	68.3	Interfacial
AS4C	234.4	3.58	81.4	Strong Matrix
Epoxy	3.6	0.09	---	---

by the embedded single fiber test while the properties of the fiber are unchanged by the different surface treatments. It is also important to note that the change in the level of adhesion brings about an accompanying change in the interfacial failure mode (Figure 1).

3.1 On-axis properties Average values of the on-axis (tension and compression) properties for the three unidirectional composite systems are listed in Table 2.

3.1.1 [0]₁₂-Tension. It should be noted that the fiber volume fractions of different panels are not identical, therefore, the values of the longitudinal tensile modulus and tensile strength were linearly scaled to the average fiber volume fraction of 67.7%. A comparison among the average longitudinal moduli of the three composite systems shows little difference of statistical significance. The average longitudinal tensile strengths (σ_{11}^f) of the three composite materials are shown in Figure 2. It is interesting to note that when the ISS is increased from the low to the intermediate values (i.e an increase in the ISS of about 83%) the strength increases by about 25%. However, when the ISS is further increased to the high level (i.e. additional increase in the ISS by about 19%), the strength shows no increase (within the error band). The change in the tensile strength as a function of fiber-matrix adhesion is attributed to the change in the failure modes and failure processes.

The AU-4/Epoxy composites, which have the lowest value of ISS, do not show much surface damage but undergo extensive internal damage, primarily in the form of delamination that extended deep into the end-tabs. The weakened interface is not able to efficiently transfer the load from critically stressed fibers to the lower-stressed neighboring regions and the composite is weak.

Table 2 - Summary of On-Axis Property Results for Carbon/Epoxy Composites

Test	AU-4/Epoxy	AS-4/Epoxy	AS-4C/Epoxy
[0] ₁₂ Tensile Modulus E ₁₁ (GPa)	130 ± 9	138 ± 5	150 ± 9
[0] ₁₂ Tensile Strength σ ₁₁ ^f (MPa)	1403 ± 107	1890 ± 143	2044 ± 256
[0] ₁₂ Compressive Modulus E _{1c} (GPa)	131 ± 8	126 ± 9	153 ± 8
[0] ₁₂ Compressive Strength σ _{1c} ^f (MPa)	679 ± 116	911 ± 180	1174 ± 207
[0] ₁₂ 3-Point Flexural Modulus E _{1B} (GPa)	154 ± 6	136 ± 11	147 ± 5
[0] ₁₂ 3-Point Flexural Strength σ _{1B} ^f (MPa)	1662 ± 92	1557 ± 102	1827 ± 52

The AS-4/Epoxy composites, where the interface is stronger than that in AU-4/Epoxy, show extensive fiber-matrix splitting. This type of failure is described as "brush-like." An interfacial crack grows parallel to the fibers and acts as a "crack-arrester" thereby relieving the stresses from the critically stressed regions.

In the AS-4C/Epoxy specimens where the interfacial shear strength has been noted to be the highest, cracks have cut across the specimen section with little fiber-matrix splitting. The strong interface in AS-4C/Epoxy specimens is able to sustain larger loads. Thus, the "crack-blunting" mechanism that was active in AS-4/Epoxy specimens is not operative in AS-4C/Epoxy specimens. When fibers start breaking the strong interface at the broken ends of the fibers does not fail and a crack propagates perpendicular to the fiber axis. Therefore, any gain in the strength due to the higher ISS is offset by the increased "notch-sensitivity" of the material.

From these failure modes it can be concluded that the tensile strength increases with increasing interfacial shear strength only as long as the failure is primarily interfacial. When the interfacial bond strength is excessive, the failure mode changes from interfacial to matrix and the composite behaves like a brittle material, i.e. it becomes "notch-sensitive." Thus, excessive fiber-matrix bond strength may have detrimental effect on the longitudinal tensile strength of the composite¹¹.

3.1.2 [0]₁₂-Compression. The compression tests were conducted on an IITRI compression fixture. The average (of 12 specimens each) compressive modulus for the three different composite materials is listed in Table 2. For the purpose of comparison among the three composite materials, the average compressive modulus and strength values were linearly scaled to the average fiber volume fraction of 66.1%.

There is little change (within the experimental error) in the compressive modulus between AU-4/Epoxy and AS-4/Epoxy, even though the ISS of the later is about 83% higher than that of the former. Between the AS-4/Epoxy and AS-4C/Epoxy, there is an increase in the compressive modulus of about 29% for a corresponding increase in the ISS of about 19%. The increase in the compressive modulus of the AS-4C/Epoxy is not because of the increased adhesion between fiber and matrix, but it is due to the presence of the high modulus brittle interphase around the AS-4C graphite fibers.

The average compressive strength values for the three composite materials are shown in Figure 3. In spite of the large scatter in the experimental data, the increasing trend in the compressive strength with increasing ISS is clearly indicated. Experimental results obtained on the same three groups of composites have shown that the transverse tensile strength increases significantly when the fiber-matrix adhesion is increased. Therefore, the increase in the compressive strength corresponding to the increase in the ISS from the low to the intermediate values, and then the subsequent more rapid increase in the strength corresponding to the increase in the ISS from intermediate to the highest values suggest that both the improved shear strength between fiber and matrix coupled with the presence of the high modulus brittle interphase around the graphite fibers, and the improved transverse tensile strength of the composite contribute to the greater compressive strength of these composites.

The major failure modes identified for the three types of graphite/epoxy composites are summarized schematically in Figure 4. The schematic shows delamination and global delamination buckling for the composite having the untreated AU-4 fibers. In the composite having the surface treated AS-4 fibers the failure is initiated by local fiber microbuckling that propagates along the line of maximum shear stress. In the case of composite having the surface treated and coated AS-4C fibers, the failure is caused by the compressive failure of fibers that occurs in several planes resulting in a "stepped" fracture surface¹².

3.1.3 [0]₁₂, 3-Point Flexure. The geometry and dimensions of the [0]₁₂, 3-point flexure specimen and the calculation of the flexural modulus and flexural strength was done according to the method outlined in ASTM D-790. These values are listed in Table 2. For the purpose of comparison between different composite systems, all the flexural modulus and strength values were linearly scaled to the average V_f (=67.7%).

The average longitudinal flexural strengths for the three composite systems are shown in Figure 5. There is little difference (within the scatter band) between flexural strengths of AU-4/Epoxy and AS-4/Epoxy composites. However, the strength of AS-4C/Epoxy is about 33% higher than that of AS-4/Epoxy. Interlaminar cracks were observed both in the AU-4/Epoxy and AS-4/Epoxy composites, it suggests that in these specimens even at large aspect ratios (=60), the longitudinal flexural failure was still initiated by the interlaminar failure of the specimens. When the ISS is at its highest level (such as in the AS-4C/Epoxy), the interlaminar failure is suppressed and the fracture occurs due to tensile (or compressive failure) of the specimens. As a result, the flexural strength of the AS-4C/Epoxy composite is higher than that of the other two composites. In summary, there was little change in the longitudinal flexural properties when the ISS was increased from the low to the intermediate values. Some improvement was noticed in both the flexural stiffness and strength when the ISS was increased from the intermediate to the highest levels. The improvement in the stiffness is attributed to the presence of the high modulus interphase and that in the strength is attributed to the ability of the strong interface to suppress the interlaminar failure. The widespread interfacial failure evident in the fracture surfaces of the AU-4/Epoxy and AS-4/Epoxy specimens suggests the likelihood of the fracture initiated by the interlaminar failure in these specimens.

3.2 Off-axis Properties Average values of the off-axis properties for the three composite systems are listed in Table 3. Each entry in this table is an average of results from ten specimens.

3.2.1 [90]₁₂-Tension. Like the longitudinal tensile modulus, the transverse tensile modulus is also relatively insensitive to the ISS. Comparisons of average transverse tensile strength (σ_{22}) among the three types of composites is shown in Figure 6. In spite of the large scatter in the transverse tensile data, a strong sensitivity of the ISS to the transverse tensile strength is seen. When the ISS is increased by about 83%, the transverse tensile strength increases by about 72%. For an additional increase in the ISS by about 19%, the strength is increased by 20%.

Examination of these fracture surfaces under the SEM shows different micro-failure modes for these composites. In the AU-4/Epoxy composite, clean fiber surfaces indicate extensive interfacial failure. In addition, there is little matrix material between the fibers, i.e. the fibers are loosely held by the matrix material. The fracture surface of AS-4/Epoxy specimen shows bare fibers as well as fibers coated with matrix material. Unlike the AU-4/Epoxy specimen, the fibers in AS-4/Epoxy specimen are held together by the matrix material. Scattered fiber breaks are also seen in the fracture surfaces. In the AS-4C/Epoxy composites, where the ISS is greater than that in the AS-4/Epoxy, the fracture surface shows significantly more matrix failure. Except at a few locations where fibers are bare, almost all the fibers are coated with matrix material¹³.

3.2.2 [90]₁₂, 3-Point Flexure. All the three material systems yield similar values indicating little effect of the ISS on the transverse flexural modulus. The transverse flexural strength (σ_{22}^f), on the other hand, is highly sensitive to the ISS, Figure 7. The percentage increase in the strength is even much higher than the corresponding increase in the ISS. A 118% increase in the ISS yields an about 253% increase in the transverse flexural strength. SEM Examination of the tensile and the compressive sides of these specimens showed little difference in their fracture surface morphologies. The AU-4/Epoxy specimen fractured entirely along the interface. Fibers are separated from each other with no matrix material around them. The AS-4/Epoxy specimen also shows significant interfacial failure. However, in addition to the interfacial failure, matrix failure is seen as well. In the AS-4C/Epoxy specimen, where the ISS is the highest, the primary failure mode is the matrix failure. Some interfacial failure can also be seen.

Comparison of the transverse flexural and transverse tensile moduli and strengths shows that while both the tensile and flexural moduli are similar to each other and are insensitive to fiber-matrix adhesion, there is a significant difference between transverse flexural and transverse tensile strengths. Not only that the transverse flexural strength is more sensitive than the transverse tensile strength to the ISS, it is much higher than the transverse tensile strength.

3.2.3 Inplane Shear Response - [± 45]₃₅-Tension Test. The average values of G_{12} for the three material systems are listed in Table 3. Unexpectedly, the shear modulus of the composite containing the untreated fibers (AU-4) is higher than the ones containing the treated fibers. In the AU-4/Epoxy specimens, which are characterized as having poor fiber-matrix ISS, there will be some rotation of different plies relative to each other at small applied tensile loads due to the interply failure giving rise to an apparent increase in the modulus. The shear stress along the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers is not constant through the thickness making the assumptions required for the calculation of the modulus not valid.

A comparison of the average inplane shear strengths (τ_{12}^f) among the three composite systems is shown in **Figure 8**. The inplane shear strength is highly sensitive to the fiber-matrix ISS. For an increase of 118% in the ISS, the corresponding increase in the inplane shear strength is 162%. The increase in the inplane shear strength with the ISS is the result of different failure modes occurring in the three different groups of composites. In the AU-4/Epoxy specimens where the fibers are untreated, the failure mode is entirely interfacial. The fibers are almost completely devoid of matrix. The low ISS causes the interply failure along the interface resulting in a low shear strength of the composite. In the AS-4/Epoxy specimens where the fibers are surface treated, the major failure modes are interfacial and matrix failure with interfacial failure being more dominant. Since the ISS in the AS-4/Epoxy system is approaching the matrix shear strength⁸, a combination of the interfacial and matrix failure modes is expected. In the AS-4C/Epoxy composites where the ISS is the highest, the dominant failure mode is the matrix failure. This should be expected because the ISS in AS-4C/Epoxy is larger than the matrix

Table 3. Summary of Off-Axis Property Results for Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composites

Measurement	AU-4/Epoxy	AS-4/Epoxy	AS-4C/Epoxy
[90] ₁₂ Tensile Modulus E_{22} (GPa)	8.9 ± 0.6	9.8 ± 0.6	10.3 ± 0.6
[90] ₁₂ Tensile Strength σ_{22}^f (MPa)	18.0 ± 3.9	34.2 ± 6.2	41.2 ± 4.7
[90] ₁₂ Flexural Modulus E_{2B} (GPa)	10.2 ± 1.5	9.9 ± 0.5	10.7 ± 0.6
[90] ₁₂ Flexural Strength σ_{2B}^f (MPa)	21.4 ± 5.8	50.2 ± 3.4	75.6 ± 14.0
[±45] _{3S} Inplane Shear Modulus G_{12} (GPa)	9.1 ± 1.5	6.2 ± 0.5	6.0 ± 0.2
[±45] _{3S} Inplane Shear Strength τ_{12}^f (MPa)	37.2 ± 1.8	72.2 ± 12.4	97.5 ± 7.4
Iosipescu Inplane Shear Modulus G_{12} (GPa)	7.2 ± 0.5	6.4 ± 1.0	7.9 ± 0.4
Iosipescu Inplane Shear Strength τ_{12}^f (MPa)	55.0 ± 3.0	95.6 ± 5.1	93.8 ± 3.3
Short Beam Interlaminar Shear Strength τ_{13}^f (MPa)	47.5 ± 5.4	84.0 ± 7.0	93.2 ± 3.8

shear strength. In addition to the factors that are responsible for improving the inplane shear strength of AS-4/Epoxy composites, the brittle interphase that is present around the AS-4C fibers⁸ further helps in achieving more uniform stress transfer between adjacent fibers and between adjacent plies.

3.2.4 Inplane Shear Response - Iosipescu Shear Test. The average inplane shear moduli for the three composite systems are identical within the scatter band of results. The average inplane shear strengths of the three material systems are shown in **Figure 8**. A sharp increase in the shear strength when going from AU-4/Epoxy to AS-4/Epoxy composites is evident. The weak interface in the former does not provide much resistance to the crack front. However, unlike as in ±45°-tension tests, the inplane shear strength calculated from Iosipescu shear test method does not register any further increase in going from AS-4/Epoxy to AS-4C/Epoxy composites. In the AS-4/Epoxy composites the interface is much stronger and the fiber matrix ISS is almost equal to the matrix shear strength. Clearly, therefore, both the failure modes (interfacial and matrix failure) should be expected and the composite's inplane shear strength should increase approximately in the same ratio as the increase in the ISS (the inplane shear strength increases by 74% for a corresponding increase in the ISS of 83%). In the case of AS-4C/Epoxy composites the ISS is even higher but at the same time there exists a brittle interphase around AS-4C graphite fibers⁸. The additional increase in the ISS is not translated into the additional gain in the shear strength because the local stress concentration around the machined notch can cause a premature brittle failure of the interphase. As a result, the shear failure of the composite occurs prior to the full realization of the fiber-matrix ISS.

3.2.5 Interlaminar Shear Response - Short Beam Shear Test. The short beam shear (SBS) test was used as a basis for comparing the apparent interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), τ_{13}^f , of the carbon/epoxy composites as a function of fiber-matrix adhesion. The ILSS increases by about 77% for a corresponding increase in ISS of about 83%. Further increasing the ISS by 19%, the ILSS shows an additional increase of about 11%. A slight decrease in the rate of increase of ILSS with ISS in going from AS-4/Epoxy to AS-4C/Epoxy may suggest that almost full potential of fiber-matrix interface may have already been utilized in the AS-4/Epoxy composites and therefore further strengthening the interface (as in AS-4C/Epoxy composites) will drive the interlaminar failure to occur in the matrix resulting in only a marginal improvement in the ILSS.

A strong relationship between ISS and ILSS should be expected considering that the data from both the single fiber test (for calculating the ISS) and the SBS test (for calculating ILSS) are a relative measure of the same component of the shear stress (i.e. τ_{13}). This is not surprising considering the nature of differences in the two tests and the different equations and simplifying assumptions used in these two different methods. In the single fiber test the ISS is related to the tensile strength of the embedded fiber⁴ whereas in the SBS test the ILSS is determined from the maximum shear stress equation derived from the beam theory. When the midplane shear stress in the SBS specimen exceeds the interfacial shear stress or the matrix shear stress, whichever is smaller, the interlaminar failure is assumed to occur. In practical situations, however, the SBS specimens often show a combination of failure modes, such as delamination in several planes across the specimen depth, local crushing of the specimen by the loading pin, bending failure, etc. In addition, even the slight nonuniformities in the boundary conditions across the loading pin would destroy the symmetry of the deformed shape of the specimen resulting in a nonuniform state of shear stress.

3.3 Fracture Toughness Characterization The Mode I and Mode II testing was performed using the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End-Notched Flexure (ENF) test methods, respectively¹⁴. The summary of results is listed in Table 4.

3.3.1 Mode I Fracture Toughness (DCB Tests). To calculate the G_{IC} for each specimen, the elastic beam analysis method was employed. The average G_{IC} for the different composite systems are listed in Table 4. In all the AU-4/Epoxy DCB specimens the crack growth is not self-similar. In addition, the crack extension did not occur smoothly in these specimens, i.e. the crack progressed in 'jumps'

Table 4. Summary of Mode I and Mode II Fracture Toughness Results for [0]₂₄ Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Composites

Measurement	AU-4/Epoxy	AS-4/Epoxy	AS-4C/Epoxy	Epoxy
Mode I G_{IC} (kJ/m ²)	could not be measured	0.33 ± 0.02	0.39 ± 0.03	0.13*
Mode II G_{IIC} (kJ/m ²)	0.40 ± 0.08	1.04 ± 0.17	1.15 ± 0.13	

* The Epoxy value was calculated from K_{IC} given in Reference 13 $G_{IC} = K_{IC}^2 \frac{(1-\nu^2)}{E}$
where $E = 3.6$ GPa, $K_{IC} = 0.73$ MPa \sqrt{m} and $\nu = 0.35$.

and the crack was meandering through several planes. In such a case, it is not possible to account for the different energy absorbing mechanisms during the crack propagation.

The average values of the G_{IC} for the AS-4/Epoxy and AS-4C/Epoxy are plotted in Figure 9. For about 19% increase in the fiber-matrix ISS (see Table 1), the G_{IC} increases by about 17%. It is interesting to note that the sensitivity of the G_{IC} is similar to that of transverse tensile strength (σ_{22}^f). For the 19% increase in the ISS, the σ_{22}^f improved by about 20%. The similarity in the sensitivities of G_{IC} and σ_{22}^f to the ISS should be expected considering that the peel stress (or transverse tensile stress) dominates in both the cases. The fiber-matrix ISS of the AS-4C/Epoxy is about 19% higher than that of the AS-4/Epoxy, and in addition the graphite fibers in the former are surrounded by a thin interphase that has lower fracture toughness than the bulk matrix⁸. The dominant micromechanical event responsible for the increased Mode I fracture toughness of AS-4C/Epoxy compared to that of the AS-4/Epoxy is increased matrix deformation resulting from the improved fiber-matrix adhesion. Although the AS-4C fibers are surrounded by the low fracture toughness interphase, the gain in the composite fracture toughness from the improved adhesion is larger than the loss resulting from the brittle interphase. Thus even in the composite system having highly cross-linked brittle epoxy system, the interfacial strength must be increased to a sufficiently high level in order to maximize the composite interlaminar fracture toughness.

3.3.2 Mode II Fracture Toughness (ENF Tests). The ENF test provides a method for computing the composite interlaminar fracture toughness in a forward shear mode (Mode II)¹⁵. The validity of the ENF test for inducing pure Mode II conditions at the mid-plane of specimen has been established and the effect of friction between the crack faces has been shown to be less than 4%¹⁶. The average values of G_{IIC} for the three types

of composites are listed in **Table 4**, and the same values are shown graphically in **Figure 9**. The three composite materials having different fiber-matrix ISS yield significantly different values of the G_{IC} . The G_{IC} increases by about 160% for a corresponding increase in the ISS of about 83%. For a further increase in the ISS by about 19%, the G_{IC} registers additional increase of about 11%. Thus for a total of about 2.2 fold increase in the ISS, the G_{IC} increased by almost 2.9 times.

The trend in the behavior of the G_{IC} is similar to that of the interlaminar shear strength (τ_{13}^f) i.e. a large increase in the G_{IC} and τ_{13}^f when the ISS is increased from the low to the intermediate values, and only a moderate increase when the ISS is further increased from the intermediate to the high values. There is almost one-to-one correlation between τ_{13}^f and the ISS between the low and medium values of the ISS (i.e. for the 1.8 fold increase in the ISS, the τ_{13}^f increases by about 1.8 times).

When the ISS is increased to the highest level (i.e. in the AS-4C/Epoxy composite), however, the increase in the G_{IC} is not as significant. The improved fiber-matrix adhesion will tend to increase and the brittle interphase around the AS-4C graphite fibers will tend to reduce the fracture toughness of these composites. When the ISS exceeds the matrix shear strength the crack will propagate through the matrix, and thus, the G_{IC} will tend to reach a plateau.

In correlating the effect of fiber-matrix adhesion on the G_{IC} and the observed failure modes, it is shown that by improving the adhesion the primary failure mode changes from interfacial failure to the matrix failure. The work required to cause matrix fracture is significantly larger than that to cause the failure of the interface having low ISS. When the fiber-matrix adhesion is strong, several energy absorbing phenomena such as, matrix deformation, matrix cracking, fiber pull-out, interfacial failure, etc. take place. As a result the G_{IC} of the composites shows significant improvement when fiber-matrix adhesion is increased. At a certain level when the interfacial strength approaches the matrix strength, the additional increase in the ISS may not yield much improvement in the fracture toughness of the composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

As a result of this study, the following conclusions can be made:

Comparison between results from the single fiber and composite tests indicate that two key parameters must be obtained from single fiber tests in order to explain composite property data. They are the level of adhesion and the failure mode, i.e. interfacial or matrix. The embedded single fiber fragmentation test has been shown to be both a predictor of changes in composite properties brought about by changes in fiber-matrix adhesion and a useful research tool which not only quantitatively measures fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength but also identifies failure modes.

Fiber-matrix adhesion affects composite properties in different ways depending on the state of stress created at the fiber-matrix interphase.

4.1 On-Axis Properties:

Composite 0° Tensile Strength increases with increasing interfacial shear strength only as long as the failure is interfacial. If the interfacial strength is too weak, the composite fails prematurely because of cumulative weakening of the material. When interfacial bond strength is excessive, the failure mode changes from interfacial to matrix and the composite behaves like a brittle material, i.e. it becomes more "notch-sensitive" which may have a detrimental effect on the longitudinal tensile strength of the composite.

Composite 0° Compressive Strength. Increasing fiber-matrix adhesion increases composite compressive strength by increasing the load necessary to cause transverse tensile failure of the interface due to Poisson's effect. Delamination failure is reduced in favor of microbuckling of fibers. Further increasing the adhesion by use of the brittle interphase provides strong lateral support to the graphite fibers allowing them to be compressively loaded to their maximum capacity.

Composite 0° Flexural Strength. There was little change in the longitudinal flexural properties when the ISS was increased from the low to the intermediate values. Improvement was noticed in both the flexural stiffness and strength when the ISS was increased from the intermediate to the highest levels due to the presence of the high modulus interphase and its ability to suppress the interlaminar failure.

4.2 Off-Axis Properties:

Composite 90° Transverse Tensile and Flexural Strength. The transverse tensile strength increases with increasing fiber-matrix adhesion. The transverse flexural test results indicate that fiber-matrix adhesion has a stronger influence on the transverse flexural strength than on the transverse tensile strength. The transverse flexural strength can be a very sensitive indicator of the interfacial strength.

Composite Inplane Shear Strength For a proper interpretation of the inplane shear strength data from any of the three test methods, an understanding of the fiber-matrix adhesion level and the interfacial failure modes is essential. The Iosipescu method showed the least scatter and tracked changes in fiber-matrix adhesion. The $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen also tracked changes in fiber-matrix adhesion. For the highest levels of adhesion with matrix dominated failure, the $\pm 45^\circ$ specimen showed a greater value than the Iosipescu specimen because of the lack

of sensitivity to matrix cracking. The short beam shear specimen also paralleled the single fiber results as long as the failure mode was interfacial. At high levels of adhesion with matrix failure the specimen failed prematurely under these matrix dominated conditions.

4.3 Composite Fracture Properties: The dominant micromechanical event responsible for the increased Mode I fracture toughness is increased matrix deformation resulting from the improved fiber-matrix adhesion. Even the low fracture toughness interphase surrounding the AS-4C fibers increase the composite fracture toughness as a result of improved adhesion.

The effect of fiber-matrix adhesion on the G_{Ic} and the observed failure modes is shown to be a primary failure mode change from interfacial failure to the matrix failure. When the interfacial strength approaches the matrix strength, the additional increase in the ISS may not yield much improvement in the fracture toughness of the composite.

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Figure 1. Schematic Diagram illustrating the three failure modes detected with increasing fiber-matrix adhesion. The drawings represent a single fiber in the epoxy matrix and subjected to shear causing the fiber to fracture. At low levels of adhesion - frictional debonding; at intermediate levels - interfacial crack growth; at the highest levels matrix cracking perpendicular to the fiber axis.

Figure 2. Comparison among the longitudinal tensile strength of the three composite materials. The strength of AS-4/Epoxy is about 25% higher than that of AU-4/Epoxy. However, the strength of AS-4C/Epoxy is similar to that of AS-4/Epoxy.

Figure 3. Comparison among the average longitudinal compressive strength of the three types of Carbon/Epoxy composites. The composite having the stronger fiber-matrix adhesion yields higher compressive strength.

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Figure 4. Schematics of the major failure modes detected for the three types of Carbon/Epoxy composite materials. These failure modes are: global delamination buckling, local fiber microbuckling, and fiber compressive failure for the composites having the poor, intermediate, and the highest levels of fiber-matrix adhesion, respectively.

Figure 5. Longitudinal flexural strengths of the three types of Carbon/Epoxy composite materials. There is insignificant change in the flexural strength for the three composite materials.

Figure 6. Transverse tensile strength of the three composite materials. In spite of the large scatter in the experimental data, a strong sensitivity of the ISS on the transverse strength can be seen.

Figure 7. Transverse flexural strength of the three types of Carbon/Epoxy composite materials. The strength increases significantly with the ISS.

Figure 8. Comparison among the shear strengths determined from the three different test methods. When the fiber-matrix interphase is not brittle, the Iosipescu shear test yields the higher shear strength. The interlaminar shear strength is closer to the inplane shear strength determined from the Iosipescu shear test method.

Figure 9. Comparison between the Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness of the three composite materials. The Mode II fracture toughness is about 3 times higher than the Mode I fracture toughness.

